

A Selective Machine Learning Approach for Double-Threshold Spectrum Sensing

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Abstract—Spectrum sensing based on energy detection is widely used due to its low complexity, but its performance degrades under low signal-to-noise ratios and noise uncertainty. Double-threshold energy detection introduces an uncertainty region between two thresholds, where reliable decisions are difficult to obtain using conventional methods. This paper proposes a selective machine learning assisted spectrum sensing method in which a simple classifier is applied only when the sensed energy falls within the uncertainty region, while energy detection is used for confident decisions. Simulation results show that the proposed method achieves detection accuracies between approximately 71% and 99% under different signal-to-noise ratio and noise uncertainty conditions. Machine learning is invoked only for a subset of sensing instances, resulting in low average classification times below 1 ms.

Index Terms—spectrum sensing, cognitive radio, double threshold detection, machine learning assisted detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Spectrum sensing is a core function in cognitive radio networks, which allows secondary users (SUs) to detect the activity of primary users (PUs) before accessing the spectrum. This has motivated extensive research on dynamic spectrum access mechanisms and a wide range of spectrum sensing techniques, such as matched filtering, energy detection, and cyclostationary feature detection, each characterized by different assumptions, complexity levels, and implementation requirements [1].

Among these methods, energy detection is frequently considered due to its low complexity and independence from prior knowledge of PU signals; however, its performance is known to be affected by noise uncertainty [2], [3]. To address this issue, noise-uncertainty-aware sensing schemes have been proposed, for instance Bayesian formulations that explicitly model uncertainty in noise power [4]. Similar sensing challenges are discussed in the context of wideband spectrum sensing and emerging wireless systems, where sensing must be performed over large bandwidths and diverse signal structures [5], [6].

Double-threshold spectrum sensing has been introduced as an extension of conventional energy detection by defining two decision thresholds and an intermediate region where re-sensing is performed. Variations of this

approach have been studied and they take into account noise uncertainty and low-SNR conditions, including adaptive threshold designs [7] and eigenvalue-based double-threshold methods that rely on covariance matrix statistics rather than explicit noise power estimation [8].

Machine learning techniques have also been applied to spectrum sensing, particularly in cooperative sensing scenarios. In [9], cooperative spectrum sensing is formulated as a classification problem using energy measurements collected from multiple SUs, and both supervised and unsupervised learning methods are investigated. Deep learning-based spectrum sensing approaches that operate on received signal representations are studied in [10], and a comprehensive review of deep neural network architectures and learning paradigms for spectrum sensing is provided in [11]. An overview of machine learning-based cooperative sensing architectures and design considerations is presented in [12]. Energy-efficient cooperative spectrum sensing strategies based on machine learning are examined in [13], and learning-assisted sensing methods tailored to OFDM systems are proposed in [14]. More recently, reinforcement learning has been used in cooperative sensing frameworks to control the participation of SUs during sensing [15].

This paper proposes a selective machine learning-assisted spectrum sensing approach that integrates conventional double-threshold energy detection with learning-based decision making. Energy detection is used for confident sensing outcomes, while a lightweight machine learning classifier is invoked only when the measured energy falls within the uncertainty region between the two thresholds.

This work focuses on trustworthy AI-based decision support under uncertain operating conditions. Therefore the present paper examines how machine learning can be integrated in a controlled and efficient way within a detection process which relates to the broader perspective of studying reliable AI-supported mechanisms for critical systems including cybersecurity in smart verticals such as healthcare [16].

The novelty of the proposed method lies in the selective

use of machine learning only for sensing instances that fall within the uncertainty region of a double-threshold detector. In this way, the method combines conventional energy detection for confident decisions with learning-based classification for ambiguous cases. This provides a trade-off between detection performance and computational cost without applying machine learning to all sensing instances.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the proposed selective machine learning-assisted spectrum sensing method, including the system model, decision process, signal model, dataset generation, and the selected classifier. Section III presents the system evaluation methodology. Section IV discusses the simulation results obtained under different signal-to-noise ratio and noise uncertainty conditions. Section V concludes the paper.

II. PROPOSED SELECTIVE ML-ASSISTED SPECTRUM SENSING METHOD

A. System Model and Decision Flow

The proposed spectrum sensing scheme combines conventional double-threshold energy detection with a selectively activated machine learning classifier. The objective is to retain the low computational cost of energy detection for a part of the sensing instances, while improving decision reliability in cases where energy-based sensing is uncertain.

The received signal is first processed using an energy detector, which computes an energy statistic over a sensing window. The result is then compared against two thresholds, denoted by λ_{low} and λ_{high} . When the measured energy is lower than λ_{low} , the channel is declared idle, while energies exceeding λ_{high} indicate PU activity.

For energy values that fall between the two thresholds, the sensing outcome cannot be determined reliably using energy detection alone due to the effects of noise uncertainty and low signal-to-noise ratios. In this region, a machine learning classifier is applied to refine the sensing decision. The classifier uses additional signal features to decide between the idle and occupied channel states.

The main idea of the proposed method is that machine learning is applied only within the uncertainty region defined by the double thresholds. Unlike fully learning-based sensing schemes, the classifier is not invoked for all sensing instances, which limits the average computational load and sensing time.

A simplified pseudocode description of the proposed sensing procedure is provided in Algorithm 1.

B. Signal Model and Dataset Generation

Spectrum sensing is modeled as a binary hypothesis testing problem over a sensing window of N complex

Algorithm 1 Proposed Spectrum Sensing Algorithm

Compute energy statistic:

$$E = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |y[n]|^2$$

if $E < \lambda_{\text{low}}$ **then**

Decide H_0 (PU absent)

else if $E > \lambda_{\text{high}}$ **then**

Decide H_1 (PU present)

else

Extract feature vector \mathbf{x} from $y[n]$

Apply trained machine learning classifier

Decide H_0 or H_1 based on classifier output

end if

baseband samples. The two hypotheses correspond to the absence or presence of a PU signal:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 : y[n] &= w[n], \\ H_1 : y[n] &= x[n] + w[n], \quad n = 1, \dots, N. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $y[n]$ denotes the received signal at the SU and $w[n] \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_w^2)$ is complex additive white Gaussian noise. Under H_0 , the channel is idle and the received signal consists only of noise. Under H_1 , the channel is occupied and $x[n]$ represents the received PU component after propagation effects.

In the occupied case, the received signal is generated as an OFDM waveform passed through a frequency-selective fading channel. A baseband OFDM burst is synthesized using random QPSK symbols across 1024 subcarriers, followed by an inverse FFT and the insertion of a cyclic prefix of length 128. A total of 30 OFDM symbols are concatenated to form the sensing window. The resulting signal is passed through a 6-tap frequency-selective Rayleigh fading channel and corrupted by additive noise. Under H_0 , only noise samples are generated.

To account for practical noise uncertainty, the noise variance σ_w^2 is not fixed but varies independently across sensing realizations. Specifically, the true noise variance is drawn uniformly in the logarithmic domain within the interval $[\sigma_{\text{est}}^2/\rho, \rho\sigma_{\text{est}}^2]$, where σ_{est}^2 is the nominal noise power assumed by the detector and ρ is a noise uncertainty factor derived from a specified uncertainty level in dB. The detector thresholds are computed using σ_{est}^2 , which leads to an ambiguity region when the true noise power deviates from this estimate.

For occupied samples, the received signal-to-noise ratio is defined as

$$\text{SNR} \triangleq \frac{\mathbb{E}[|x[n]|^2]}{\sigma_w^2}, \quad (2)$$

and is controlled by scaling the faded OFDM signal accordingly. SNR values are drawn from a low-SNR range between -22 dB and -6 dB.

The scalar energy statistic used for the double-threshold decision is computed as

$$E \triangleq \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |y[n]|^2. \quad (3)$$

Two thresholds, λ_{low} and λ_{high} , are derived under a Gaussian approximation of the energy statistic E under H_0 for a target false-alarm probability $P_{\text{fa}} = 0.05$, and expanded by a design factor to define an intermediate uncertainty region. Only sensing instances satisfying the double-threshold ambiguity condition in (4) are retained for classification.

$$\lambda_{\text{low}} \leq E \leq \lambda_{\text{high}} \quad (4)$$

Using the Gaussian approximation of the energy statistic under H_0 , the base threshold λ is selected to satisfy a target false-alarm probability P_{fa} :

$$\lambda = \sigma_{\text{est}}^2 + Q^{-1}(P_{\text{fa}}) \frac{\sigma_{\text{est}}^2}{\sqrt{N}}. \quad (5)$$

To account for noise uncertainty, a double-threshold region is formed by expanding λ with factor ρ' :

$$\lambda_{\text{low}} = \frac{\lambda}{\rho'}, \quad \lambda_{\text{high}} = \lambda \rho', \quad (6)$$

where $\rho' = 10^{\Delta_{\text{NU}}/10}$ and Δ_{NU} is the noise uncertainty level in dB.

For each retained instance, a real-valued feature vector is constructed consisting of the scalar energy statistic, a block-based energy vector obtained by partitioning the sensing window into 8 segments, and a cyclic-prefix correlation feature that exploits the redundancy introduced by the OFDM structure. These labeled feature vectors form the training dataset for the machine learning classifier, while independent full-range datasets are generated for evaluating the complete hybrid sensing system.

C. Chosen Classifier: Support Vector Machine

A support vector machine (SVM) is a supervised learning method which separates two classes by learning a decision boundary from labeled data [17]. In the proposed method, the SVM is used only to resolve sensing decisions within the uncertainty region of the double-threshold detector, where energy-based decisions are unreliable.

The SVM operates on a real-valued feature vector composed of energy-based and OFDM-related features extracted from the received signal. A nonlinear radial basis function kernel is employed to capture decision boundaries that cannot be represented by a single energy threshold. Compared to more complex learning models, SVMs offer stable performance with limited training data and modest computational requirements, which makes them suitable for the proposed selective sensing framework. Alternative classifiers, including logistic regression and random forest, were also evaluated during preliminary experiments, but

SVM achieved the best detection performance for the considered dataset.

The classifier is trained offline using only samples from the uncertainty region and is invoked during operation for these cases, while confident decisions are handled by energy detection. This selective use of machine learning improves sensing accuracy in difficult conditions while limiting computational cost and sensing time.

III. SYSTEM EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

The proposed selective ML-assisted spectrum sensing scheme is evaluated using synthetically generated datasets. The datasets are generated using Python scripts based on the signal model described in Section II.

The training dataset contains 20 000 sensing instances. Only samples whose energy statistic falls within the double-threshold region are retained, since the classifier is applied only in this region. The feature vector includes the energy statistic, an energy vector obtained by dividing the sensing window into eight blocks, and a cyclic-prefix correlation feature.

The dataset is divided into training, validation, and testing subsets using a 70%/15%/15% split. A support vector machine with a radial basis function kernel is trained using the training subset. Feature normalization is performed using standard scaling.

For system-level evaluation, separate test datasets are generated independently of the training data. First, a dataset is generated with the signal-to-noise ratio uniformly distributed over the interval from -22 dB to -6 dB. The hybrid decision procedure described in Section II is then applied to all sensing instances.

For this dataset, the confusion matrix of the hybrid detector is computed, then the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve is generated by sweeping the classifier decision threshold within the uncertainty region. Detection probability is also evaluated as a function of SNR at a fixed false alarm probability, resulting in a P_d versus SNR curve.

In a second stage, additional independent test datasets are generated for narrower SNR intervals: -18 to -12 dB, -12 to -6 dB, and -6 to 0 dB. For these datasets, experiments are performed under different noise uncertainty levels. Performance is evaluated using classification accuracy, detection probability P_d , probability of false alarm P_{fa} , the percentage of sensing instances for which the machine learning classifier is invoked (ML usage rate), and the average detection time per sensing instance.

In addition to the proposed hybrid method, baseline implementations of conventional energy detection and double-threshold energy detection were also implemented and evaluated on the same generated dataset for the low-SNR range (-18 to -12 dB). This ensures a fair comparison between the classical sensing approaches and the proposed selective machine learning-assisted detector under challenging sensing conditions.

Fig. 1. Confusion matrix of the proposed selective ML-assisted spectrum sensing method

Fig. 2. P_d vs SNR at $P_{fa} = 0.05$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of Results

The confusion matrix in Fig. 1 depicts the classification results of the proposed selective ML-assisted spectrum sensing method on an independent test dataset generated according to the evaluation methodology described in Section III.

Figure 1 shows that the proposed model produces a low number of false alarms, with only 53 idle-channel samples classified as occupied, while 769 occupied-channel samples are classified as idle. From the confusion matrix, the resulting overall accuracy is approximately 83.6%, indicating that most sensing instances are correctly classified across the considered SNR range.

Figure 2 presents the detection probability as a function of SNR for a fixed false alarm probability $P_{fa} = 0.05$, showing that P_d increases with SNR.

Detection performance is further analyzed using the ROC curve in Figure 3, which shows the relationship between P_d and P_{fa} for the proposed hybrid detector when the classifier decision threshold is varied within the uncertainty region.

Fig. 3. ROC Curve: P_d vs P_{fa}

The results reported in Table I illustrate the behavior of the proposed scheme across different signal-to-noise ratio ranges and noise uncertainty levels.

In the low-SNR range (-18 to -12 dB), energy-based decisions are unreliable, which leads to a relatively high machine learning call rate, particularly for larger noise uncertainty values. In this regime, the use of the classifier improves detection performance, but also increases the average detection time as the classifier is invoked more frequently.

For the intermediate SNR range (-12 to -6 dB), detection performance improves substantially, with near-perfect detection probability achieved for moderate and high noise uncertainty levels. Although the machine learning call rate remains relatively high in this range, the results indicate that the classifier effectively resolves ambiguous sensing instances.

In the high-SNR range (-6 to 0 dB), most sensing decisions can be made confidently using energy detection alone. Consequently, the machine learning call rate decreases, reducing the average inference time while maintaining high detection performance.

The target $P_{fa} = 0.05$ is used only to build the base threshold of the double-threshold detector. The final P_{fa} values in Table I correspond to the full hybrid method, so they are also influenced by the machine learning decisions inside the uncertainty region. For $NU = 0.5$ dB, the uncertainty region is narrow, fewer ambiguous samples are sent to the classifier, and the final decisions are more affected by thresholding, which leads to higher empirical P_{fa} . For larger uncertainty levels, more samples are handled by the classifier, which lowers P_{fa} but increases ML usage and decision time.

B. Comparison with Existing Methods

Several double-threshold spectrum sensing approaches try to solve the uncertainty region problem through re-sensing or extended observation windows [7]. Although these methods can improve detection reliability, they

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE OF THE PROPOSED DETECTOR FOR DIFFERENT SNR RANGES AND NOISE UNCERTAINTY LEVELS

SNR Range (dB)	NU (dB)	ML (%)	Acc. (%)	P_d (%)	P_{fa} (%)	Decision Time (ms)
-18 to -12	0.5	48.0	71.1	66.1	24.1	0.26
	1.0	95.8	84.6	70.97	1.98	0.48
	1.5	100.0	84.5	70.7	1.98	0.51
-12 to -6	0.5	46.4	87.2	96.34	20.7	0.23
	1.0	86.0	99.2	100.0	1.5	0.43
	1.5	97.3	99.1	100.0	1.68	0.50
-6 to 0	0.5	25.9	89.9	100.0	22.68	0.13
	1.0	56.2	99.0	100.0	2.06	0.29
	1.5	67.0	99.0	100.0	2.06	0.38

increase sensing time and energy consumption. The proposed method instead resolves uncertain cases using a lightweight classifier after a single sensing operation, avoiding repeated measurements.

Cooperative spectrum sensing techniques have also been widely studied [18], where multiple cognitive radios combine local sensing decisions at a fusion center. In contrast, the proposed method improves sensing reliability at the individual detector level without requiring cooperation or reporting overhead.

Table II compares the proposed hybrid sensing method with conventional energy detection and double-threshold sensing in the low-SNR range (-18 to -12 dB). The results show that the proposed approach significantly improves detection accuracy and reduces the false alarm probability under challenging low-SNR conditions.

Direct comparison with previously reported machine learning-based spectrum sensing methods is not straightforward, since existing studies usually rely on different signal models, datasets, channel assumptions, and evaluation protocols. For example, [19] reports detection probability values close to 1 for QPSK signals at an SNR of -10 dB using a CNN-based approach under a different experimental setup.

Inference time is not consistently reported in the literature, which limits a fair comparison of computational efficiency. In the studies that do report inference time, the reported values are generally at least around 1 ms, although obtained under different experimental conditions.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF SPECTRUM SENSING METHODS AT LOW SNR -18 TO -12

Method	Acc. (%)	P_d (%)	P_{fa} (%)
Energy Detection	53.0	55.0	49.0
Double Threshold	53.0	35.0	29.0
Proposed Hybrid ML	84.6	71.0	2.0

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated a hybrid spectrum sensing scheme which combines energy detection with selective machine learning assistance under noise uncertainty. A double-threshold detector separates confident and uncertain sensing instances, with machine learning applied only

within the uncertainty region to utilize additional signal features.

Simulation results show reliable detection performance under low SNR and noise uncertainty while maintaining low sensing latency. Because machine learning is invoked only for uncertain cases, the approach reduces the number of samples that require classification. The proposed framework therefore provides a practical trade-off between detection performance, computational efficiency, and sensing latency for cognitive radio systems with strict timing and energy constraints.

Future work will focus on validating the proposed method using real-world measurements. In particular, the model will be tested on experimentally collected spectrum data in order to evaluate its performance under practical channel conditions, hardware impairments, and realistic noise variations. This will provide further insight into the behavior and practical applicability of the proposed sensing framework in real cognitive radio environments.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by a grant of the European Commission no. 101183162 (ANTIDOTE project) and of the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS/CCCDI - UEFISCDI, project number PN-IV-P8-8.1-PRE-HE-ORG-2024-0236, within PNC DI IV.

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